

WHAT WE'LL SEE DOWN

TWO PATHWAYS

TO ZERO EMISSIONS FROM BUILDINGS

Annex A:

Space Heating Electrification – Impact on the Ontario Electricity Grid and Retail Rates

June 2025

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Space Heating Electrification –

Impact on the Ontario Electricity Grid and Retail Rates

February 6, 2025

Space Heating Electrification – Impact on the Ontario Electricity Grid and Retail Rates

Executive Summary

Space heating is a major contributor to environmental emissions in Ontario because most buildings are heated using natural gas and some with propane or heating oil.

Federal, provincial and municipal governments are encouraging the electrification of space heating to cleaner technologies, especially air source heat pumps (ASHPs) with electrical resistance heaters (ERHs) for backup when outdoor temperatures are very cold and ASHPs become less effective.

This report presents the results of an analysis of the electricity system to determine the impact if ASHP's are used for building heating. The analysis shows that:

- The electricity system capacity factor will drop approximately in half if we electrify space heating with ASHPs where natural gas is currently used.
- The drop in capacity factor will result in electricity rates that will more than double, not including general price inflation.
- The higher electricity rates combined with greater electricity use for ASHPs will result in a tripling of monthly energy bills for consumers, not including general price inflation.
- In a net-zero electricity system the amount of surplus clean electricity and discarded thermal energy, which could be used for building heating, will each be larger than the useful electric energy supplied to consumers for their ASHPs.
- The amount of new zero-emissions dependable generating capacity required to achieve net-zero by 2050 is much larger than Ontario's historical ability to add new electrical capacity in that period.
- Based on experience with heating buildings in cold climate countries in Europe and Asia it would be prudent to investigate alternatives to widespread ASHP electrification of building heating.

This report also recommends that community thermal networks (TNs) and community thermal energy storage (TES) be included in the integrated energy planning process in the Province of Ontario along with the planning of the future supplies of electricity, natural gas and other fuels. TN's will help reduce the needed expansion of the electricity system to a more realizable level. However, to include community TNs in the planning process, communities will need to be funded to undertake building heating planning as part of the integrated energy planning process.

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Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this report:

ASHP – Air Source Heat Pump
APO – IESO’s Annual Planning Outlook
BI – Boltzmann Institute
CCGT - Combined Cycle Gas Turbine plant
CF – Capacity Factor
CO₂ – carbon dioxide gas
CP – abbreviation used for Carbon Price expressed in \$/tonne CO₂
DES – District Energy Systems
DHS - District Heating Systems
DOE – US Department of Energy
EIA – US Energy Information Administration
EPA – US Environmental Protection Agency
ERH – Electric Resistance Heating
EV – Electric Vehicle
GA – Global Adjustment charge
GSHP – Ground Source Heat Pump
GW – gigawatt (1,000,000,000 watts of power)
GWh – gigawatthour (energy equal to 1 GW power consumption for 1 hour)
H₂ – Hydrogen gas
HOEP - Hourly Ontario Electricity Price
IESO - Independent Electricity System Operator
kg – kilogram (1,000 grams)
kW – kilowatt (1,000 watts of power)
kWh – kilowatt-hour (energy equal to 1 kW power consumption for 1 hour)
M.BTU – Million BTU
MIDAC – Market Intelligence & Data Analysis Corporation
MoEE - Ontario's Ministry of Energy and Electrification
MW – Megawatt (1,000,000 watts of power)
MWh – megawatt-hour (energy equal to 1 MW power consumption for 1 hour)
NERC – North American Electric Reliability Corporation
NG – Natural Gas
NREL – US National Renewable Energy Laboratory
NZ – Net-Zero

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OEB – Ontario Energy Board

OPG – Ontario Power Generation

OSPE – Ontario Society of Professional Engineers

RNG – Renewable Natural Gas

SBG – Surplus Base-load Generation

SCGT - Simple Cycle Gas Turbine plant

SMR – Small Modular Reactor

t/yr – metric tonnes per year (1 tonne = 1,000 kg)

TN – Thermal Networks

TES – Thermal Energy Storage

TW – terawatt (1,000,000,000,000 watts of power)

TWh – terawatt-hour (energy equal to 1 TW power consumption for 1 hour)

1. Introduction

Space heating is a major contributor to environmental emissions in Ontario because most buildings are heated using natural gas and some with propane or heating oil.

Federal, provincial and municipal governments are encouraging the electrification of space heating to cleaner technologies especially air source heat pumps (ASHPs) with electrical resistance heaters (ERHs) for backup when outdoor temperatures are very cold and ASHPs become less effective. Alternatives to ASHPs have not received much government support due to the higher cost of those technologies. For example, ground source heat pumps (GSHPs) are approximately double the cost of ASHPs. The low cost of natural gas in North America compared to Europe has also discouraged the widespread deployment of district heating systems in Canada relative to their popularity in Europe.

The support for ASHPs has been based on insufficient modelling and analysis of the impact of large scale deployment of ASHPs on the electricity system and the resulting impact on the future price of electricity. Converting to ASHPs may eliminate NG consumption and GHG emissions at individual buildings, but the increased emissions for electricity generation (now, and for many years until NG is eliminated from generation) may result in very little change (up or down) to provincial or national emissions. Early converters to ASHPs get a considerable subsidization of their electricity rate. The cost of expanding the electricity system is shared by all residential, commercial and industrial consumers. Also, electricity rates for residential and small commercial consumers are set based on the average cost to provide electric energy in kilowatt-hours, not on the

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incremental cost to meet the new peak demand in kilowatts. Eventually, as more consumers convert to ASHPs their electricity rates collectively will approach the true cost of supplying the incremental demand. Consumers are not aware of this unavoidable natural adjustment that will take place as more consumers convert to ASHPs. Future electricity rates and monthly bills for electricity consumers are therefore going to rise much faster than normal inflation if the conversion to ASHPs is aggressively pursued by various levels of government.

The Boltzmann Institute (BI) wanted to analyse the future impact on the electricity grid, electricity rates and home monthly bills if ASHPs continue to be aggressively pursued by governments. BI had modelled the hourly heating demands for Ontario but did not have an electrical grid model to forecast future electricity rates.

Market Intelligence & Data Analysis Corporation (MIDAC) had already developed a simplified electricity grid model for the Ontario Society of Professional Engineers (OSPE) to analyze the impact on retail electricity rates in Ontario in order to decarbonize the generation fleet. That grid model had the hourly energy balances and cost algorithms needed to calculate the resulting electricity rates and monthly bills as grid capacity was increased to meet the higher winter electricity demands from ASHPs.

BI asked MIDAC to assist them in forecasting the retail electricity rate impacts of different space heating options. This report summarizes the results of the detailed analysis carried out by MIDAC at the request of the BI.

2. Background and Methodology

Governments in many countries are encouraging the transition to cleaner heating systems by imposing a carbon price or tax on fossil fuel use. As the carbon price rises, the annual cost of fossil fuel will eventually overwhelm the lower capital cost of the fossil fuel burning equipment and people will voluntarily switch to cleaner heating technologies.

A consumer would of course look at the total all-in cost of the various options to heat their homes. They would compare the cost of financing the purchase and annual energy and maintenance costs of each option.

Unfortunately, today, consumers only have the current cost of fossil fuels and the current cost of electricity to guide their decisions on which energy technologies to use. Therefore, consumers cannot make informed decisions until they have reliable future costs of each of the component of costs, at least in terms of constant dollars.

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The situation with electricity is more difficult because future electricity costs will, in part, be determined by the amount of system expansion needed to accommodate all the heating needs of those who electrify their home heating. Home heating is a significant load relative to the traditional electrical loads that the electricity system currently supplies. For residential consumers, heating loads are a larger load than the combined, non-heating electrical loads for lighting, appliances, air conditioning, fans/blowers, electronic equipment, EVs, etc.

This report forecasts the future electricity price in constant 2022 CAN dollars for different heating options. Constant dollars are used to avoid the distortions that would occur if we tried to forecast inflation rates many years into the future. The 2022 year was used because cost data from dependable industry sources is available for that year.

MIDAC's simulation model includes an hourly energy balance between supply and demand. This ensures the analysis meets the North American Electric Reliability Corporation (NERC) reliability criteria for high voltage power systems by ensuring natural gas (NG) generation is available as a last resort to fill in any supply demand gaps from other generation. The simulation user can choose to eliminate that NG supply by increasing the other generation capacities including renewable natural gas (RNG) generation or by adding electrical storage. The user also decides the supply mix and can select the amount and combinations of various generation technologies to minimize electricity costs and/or emissions.

The choice of dependable base-load generation (hydroelectric, nuclear, NG or RNG) or variable generation (solar and wind) or electrical storage best suited to supply the consumer load will depend on various factors that the user will better appreciate after working with the simulation program. In general, consumer load that persists round the clock throughout the year is more economically supplied using base-load dependable generation. More variable consumer load that does not persist around the clock can be supplied more economically by variable generation, storage or RNG operating at lower capacity factors. RNG is limited in availability, but it is carbon neutral. The simulation program provides the user with the RNG annual usage so any limit to its use can be respected by the user. In this report RNG use is limited to 6 TWh of electricity production per year in Ontario.

When load only occurs primarily in a specific season like heating in winter or cooling in summer, the cost of supplying that load generally is higher due to the lower capacity factors of the equipment used to meet that load. Fortunately, Ontario has had almost as much additional electrical load for heating in the winter as it has had in air conditioning load in the summer. Most homes in

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Ontario are heated with fossil fuels but some are heated with electricity. The winter peak on a cold winter day is only about 5% to 10% less than the summer peak on a hot day. However, that difference has been shrinking in the past several years as more people electrify their space heating using ASHPs. A widespread conversion from natural gas space heating to ASHPs is the subject of this report.

The simulation program keeps track of each technology's utilization and its fixed and variable costs to provide a total system cost. The simulation user can adjust the supply mix to minimize costs and/or emissions or limit the amount of annual fuel use such as RNG.

This report presents the results of the study of the impact of space heating electrification for two calendar years - 2022 and 2050.

The year 2022 was chosen for the simulation analysis for two reasons. Firstly, calendar 2022 was a moderate weather year, during the 6 years from 2018 to 2023, that BI had produced hourly space heating data for Ontario. A normal weather year is preferred for simulation analysis. By serving the load every hour for a normal weather year and by also adding 15% reserve generation, we can in practice meet the NERC reliability criteria without having to introduce more complex math to prove the criteria has been met.

Secondly, 2022 has the same calendar structure as 2050. Year 2050 was important to study because that is the year the federal government wants to achieve net-zero emissions for the economy. Also, the simulation model requires a known reference year to calibrate the production variability of each generation technology with respect to both weather effects and random plant outages. Therefore 2022 could conveniently be used as a reference year to calibrate the simulation model for both study years 2022 and 2050.

To obtain reliable cost estimates when analyzing the electricity system performance in future years it is very important to reflect the hourly variability of various generation sources. It's the hourly variability of various generation sources that determines the amount of backup generation or storage that is needed to serve load every hour all year. The simulation program does this by taking a known historical year and "normalizing" the output of each technology type against its installed nameplate capacity. Generating units that have been taken out of service for extended outages or refurbishment programs are removed from the installed nameplate capacity.

The "normalization" process converts the reference year actual hourly output for each generation technology into a percentage of the installed nameplate capacity using the values from 0 to 1 rather than 0% to 100%. The normalized hourly

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values of the production can then be multiplied by the installed nameplate in the study year to get the expected actual output for that hour in the study year. The normalization process ensures the production profile (or shape) hour by hour in the study year exactly matches the reference year and is adjusted only to reflect the change in installed nameplate capacity. This process captures the production variability of each generation technology due to either weather effects or outages.

Because this normalization process is static it only reflects what happened in the reference year. That is another reason for selecting a year with average weather. The predictive capability of the model can be improved by running the simulation for several reference years. That would also provide a range of cost predictions to reflect variations in weather and random outage history. However, to keep the modeling effort reasonable, the MIDAC simulation for this report was done for only one reference year. A discussion of the simulation uncertainties inherent in the MIDAC simulation methodology is contained in more detail in Appendix B of this report.

The MIDAC simulation model does not automatically seek a performance goal like the lowest cost supply mix. The process of finding the lowest cost mix is manually performed by the simulation program user. The user inputs or “sweeps through” a series of increasing or decreasing installed capacities (one generation technology is reduced while a second one is increased) to see the resulting electricity price. When a minimum electricity price is found, the user then runs through the same process again varying the installed capacity of a third generation technology and so forth. With only 2 generation technologies the process is easy and quick. When there are several technologies, the process has to be repeated first for each technology and then the user needs to go back and double check that the minimum cost point has not shifted because of the changes the user made in subsequent generation capacity adjustments. It’s an iterative process that takes more time with a larger list of technologies. For two generation technologies once the zero-emission point is achieved, it takes only a few minutes to find the minimum cost combination of the two installed capacities. With a half dozen generation technologies, it can take 30 minutes to 1 hour of inputting (sweeping through) the various combinations of installed capacities. The simulation program contains a scratch pad on the “Study Year Input & Results” sheet for the user to save intermediate results until the minimum cost has been achieved. There is a separate “Case Archives & Charts” sheet where the results of each case can be copied to a table that is subsequently used to report the results of all the cases in one table. This report presents 13 different cases that MIDAC and BI wanted to run.

The publicly available electricity data for 2022 from the Independent Electricity System Operator (IESO) contains the hourly data for electricity demand,

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generation capability and actual production by technology type, and the imports and exports of electricity from/to other power systems (Quebec, Manitoba, New York, Michigan and Minnesota). That historical 2022 data is associated with the traditional electrical loads, before any major ASHP electrification.

The small number of buildings (approximately 10%) that were electrically heated in 2022 are included in the IESO 2022 demand data. Most of the heating related energy needs of buildings in Ontario are provided by fuels other than electricity. About 70% of buildings are heated by natural gas (NG) and are in urban areas, where NG is available. The remaining 20% of buildings are heated by oil, propane or wood.

To determine the impact on the electricity system of transitioning all NG space heated existing buildings to ASHPs in 2022, MIDAC added the ASHP electricity demand to replace the hourly useful heat from the NG furnaces to the IESO actual hourly load demand for 2022.

The IESO's 2024 Annual Planning Outlook provides the forecasted hourly load data for electricity demand for the years 2025 to 2050. The IESO 2050 forecasted load data includes future population growth, electrification of vehicles, electrification of all heating for new buildings (built after 2024) and additional industrial demand. The IESO forecasted data did not include the space or other heating of existing buildings built prior to 2025 and did not include high temperature industrial and commercial heat electrification.

To determine the impact on the electricity system of transitioning all NG space heated existing buildings to ASHPs in 2050, MIDAC added the ASHP electricity demand to replace the hourly useful heat from the NG furnaces to the IESO forecasted hourly load demand for 2050.

MIDAC did not model the impact on the electricity system in either 2022 or 2050 of other heating loads (water heating, cooking, clothes drying, etc.) for existing NG heated buildings because the hourly demand data for those loads is not available. However, to provide a more complete comparison of monthly energy costs for a typical natural gas heated home, MIDAC did add the cost of the additional 50% energy demand (relative to energy for space heating) for those non-space heating loads to the monthly 2022 and 2050 energy bills.

Up to 20% of existing buildings may be replaced by 2050 with more energy efficient buildings, however, countering this reduction in demand is the likelihood that IESO has not sufficiently increased the electricity demand from the reduced efficiency of ASHPs when outdoor temperatures are very cold. MIDAC has assumed these two effects cancel each other and therefore has not made a

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reduction in the space heating demand of existing buildings that are replaced by 2050.

One additional important point regarding the MIDAC simulation results. Ontario retail electricity rates are different for each of several major consumer classes ranging from residential to large industrial consumers. Also, there are different retail price plan choices consumers can subscribe to. For example, the residential consumer can choose from among 3 different regulated price plans. To simplify the simulation analysis MIDAC does not simulate the electricity rates for each of the retail price plans for each of the consumer classes. The MIDAC simulation computes the total cost of operating the electricity system for one year and then divides that cost by the total energy delivered to consumers in the year. That simplification produces an average retail rate paid by all consumers collectively. That average rate is then reported in the simulation results and used to calculate the average monthly electricity bill for a typical home. This means that a specific consumer's monthly electricity bill may be different than the figure reported in the simulation results. Appendix B discusses the simulation uncertainties in more detail for readers who are interested.

3. Electrification Impacts on Costs, Rates and Emissions

MIDAC wanted to establish a baseline of 3 cases before electrification of space heating which could be compared with the IESO data for 2022 and 2050. These cases were numbered 1 to 3.

BI wanted to analyze the impact of 9 cases covering various electrification options using Air Source Heat Pumps (ASHPs) with either NG or Electrical Resistance Heating (ERH) backup on very cold days. BI also wanted to analyse an additional case where the electricity system emissions were net-zero but existing buildings remained on NG heating. In each case, 100% electrified heating demand matches the total 2022 at-building heating with NG inferred from OEB and Statistics Canada NG monthly consumption data. These 10 cases were numbered 4 to 13.

The 13 cases are listed below with their case numbers for both the 2022 and 2050 years:

1. IESO present grid before space heating electrification of existing buildings, \$0 Carbon Price
 2. IESO present grid before space heating electrification of existing buildings, \$65 Carbon Price
 3. IESO present grid before space heating electrification of existing buildings, \$170 Carbon Price
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4. IESO present grid, 0% conversion of heating using ASHP with ERH supplementary heat, \$65 Carbon Price (same as case 2 above)
5. IESO present grid, 5% conversion of heating using ASHP with ERH supplementary heat, \$65 Carbon Price
6. IESO present grid, 100% conversion of heating using ASHP with ERH supplementary heat, \$65 Carbon Price
7. Future net-zero grid, Hybrid ASHP with NG furnace heating below +4 deg. C, \$0 Carbon Price
8. Future net-zero grid, Hybrid ASHP with NG furnace heating below +4 deg. C, \$170 Carbon Price
9. Future net-zero grid, no NG use, ERH heating, \$170 Carbon Price
10. Future net-zero grid, no NG use, ASHP with ERH supplementary heating, \$170 Carbon Price
11. Future net-zero grid, no NG use, ASHP with ERH heating below +4 deg. C, \$170 Carbon Price
12. Future net-zero grid, no NG use,, Hybrid ASHP with ERH heating below -8 deg. C, \$170 Carbon Price
13. Future net-zero grid but space heating remains on NG furnaces.

Cases 4, 5 and 6 were designed to see the impact of a small amount of electrification during the early transition period on the energy bills of those who did and did not electrify their space heating. These cases allow us to see the degree to which people who do not electrify their space heating subsidize those that do in the early transition period. It also allows us to see the degree to which those that do electrify their space heating are subsidized by those that did not electrify in the early transition period. However, as the transition progresses from case 4 to case 6, those that switched to ASHPs early in the process will see their electricity bills rise rapidly as the amount of subsidization decreases, then ceases, when the rest of the population transitions to ASHPs.

Cases 7 and 8 allow us to see the impact on consumers if they install ASHPs but continue to use NG heating at temperatures below +4 deg. C. These cases represent a two-step transitional strategy for a consumer who wants to replace an existing air conditioner with a similar-sized ASHP, with no need for costly electrical upgrades, for a partial transition for the 20-year life of the new equipment. The consumer would eventually make the final step to net-zero heating equipment before 2050. Hopefully the available equipment at that time will be superior in performance and lower in capital cost expressed in constant dollars.

Cases 9 through 12 allow us to see the impact on consumers of 4 different net-zero space heating transitions. The most expensive in terms of ongoing energy costs is the use of ERH for all the heating. The least expensive in terms of ongoing energy costs is the use of ASHPs with ERH as supplementary heating at

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all temperatures. The monthly bills do not include the cost of the heating equipment. The heating equipment cost will vary depending on technology choice and whether the building’s electrical distribution panel is able to accommodate the additional electricity load for space heating.

Case 13 has been added to see the amount of surplus electricity and discarded thermal energy that could be available in a net-zero electricity system without electrification of space heating. This is a particularly interesting case because it shows that there is sufficient surplus energy to meet all spacing heating needs. However, that surplus energy requires a community heat recovery, distribution and storage capability to make the energy available as a heating option.

The forecasted monthly bills for electricity and NG are shown in Table 3-1, below, for the 2022 year for the 13 cases.

Table 3-1
Monthly Energy Bills for a Typical Home – 2022 Year

Case Number	Elect Bill	NG Bill	Total
Case 1 – no change, \$0 CP	\$112	\$75	\$186
Case 2 – no change, \$65 CP	\$114	\$98	\$213
Case 3 – no change, \$170 CP	\$119	\$137	\$256
Case 4 – 0% conversion, NG htg, \$65 CP	\$114	\$98	\$213
Case 5a – 5% conversion, NG home, \$65 CP	\$118	\$98	\$216
Case 5b – 5% conversion, ASHP home, \$65 CP	\$250	\$0	\$250
Case 6 – 100% conversion, ASHP+ERH, \$65 CP	\$381	\$0	\$381
Case 7 – Hybrid ASHP+NG, \$0 CP	\$153	\$67	\$221
Case 8 – Hybrid ASHP+NG, \$170 CP	\$153	\$123	\$276
Case 9 – ERH, \$170 CP	\$1,135	\$0	\$1135
Case 10 - ASHP+ERH Supplement, \$170 CP	\$690	\$0	\$690
Case 11 - ASHP+ERH < +4 C, \$170 CP	\$1,095	\$0	\$1,095
Case 12 - ASHP+ERH < -8 C, \$170 CP	\$857	\$0	\$857
Case 13 – Net-zero Grid, NG heating, \$170 CP	\$132	\$137	\$269

Notes: All dollars are in constant 2022\$. Rounding to a whole \$ affects totals.
 Cases 7 to 13 have net-zero electricity grids.
 Cases 9 through 12 are net-zero for both electricity and heating.
 Case 5a is Case 5 but only for the NG heating home.
 Case 5b is Case 5 but only for the ASHP heated home.

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Only cases 9 to 12 have net-zero GHG emissions for both the electricity system (electricity grid) and space heating. Case 13 would also be net-zero if a community thermal network (TN) with thermal energy storage (TES) capability existed in urban areas to recover the surplus electricity and thermal energy from electricity production.

What is particularly noteworthy from Table 3-1 is the large increase in the monthly bill of the ASHP homeowner in Case 5 between the beginning (Case 5b, 5% conversion) and end (Case 6, 100% conversion) of the heating system conversions by his/her neighbours. The ASHP homeowner's monthly bill rises from \$250 to \$381 after the neighbours complete the conversion of their homes. This is a substantial increase in the ASHP homeowner's electricity bill in the years after the ASHP is installed and does not include general inflationary increases. The rapid rise in electricity monthly bills for ASHP homeowners is the result of rising electricity rates to pay for the expansion of the electricity system as more people convert to ASHP heating systems. These cases are before the costly transition to a net-zero electricity supply. The simulation shows the electricity rate at the beginning of the conversion process is 16 cents/kWh. At the end of the process the electricity rate will be 22 cents/kWh expressed in constant 2022\$.

When the conversion begins, the ASHP homeowner is being subsidized heavily by neighbours who have not converted their heating systems to ASHPs. The reason this happens is that electricity rates are the same for everyone. At the start of the transition, the cost of expanding the electricity system for the first few homeowners falls on everyone, even the many people who have not converted. However, as more people convert, the cost of the power system expansion eventually falls on everyone who has caused the expansion. At the end of the transition process, the electricity bill more accurately reflects the cost of expanding the power system to accommodate space heating for everyone.

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The forecasted monthly bills for electricity and NG are shown in Table 3-2 below for the 2050 year for the 13 cases that were analyzed.

Table 3-2
Monthly Energy Bills for a Typical Home – 2050 Year

Case Number	Elect Bill	NG Bill	Total
Case 1 – no change, \$0 CP	\$108	\$75	\$183
Case 2 – no change, \$65 CP	\$120	\$98	\$219
Case 3 – no change, \$170 CP	\$140	\$137	\$277
Case 4 – 0% conversion, NG heating, \$65 CP	\$120	\$98	\$219
Case 5a – 5% conversion, NG home, \$65 CP	\$123	\$98	\$221
Case 5b – 5% conversion, ASHP home, \$65 CP	\$260	\$0	\$260
Case 6 – 100% conversion, ASHP+ERH, \$65 CP	\$351	\$0	\$351
Case 7 – Hybrid ASHP+NG, \$0 CP	\$201	\$67	\$268
Case 8 – Hybrid ASHP+NG, \$170 CP	\$201	\$123	\$324
Case 9 – ERH, \$170 CP	\$1,050	\$0	\$1,050
Case 10 - ASHP+ERH Supplement, \$170 CP	\$632	\$0	\$632
Case 11 - ASHP+ERH < +4 C, \$170 CP	\$1,002	\$0	\$1002
Case 12 - ASHP+ERH < -8 C, \$170 CP	\$758	\$0	\$758
Case 13 – Net-zero Grid, NG heating, \$170 CP	\$178	\$137	\$314

Notes: All dollars are in constant 2022\$. Rounding to a whole \$ affects totals.
 Cases 7 to 13 have net-zero electricity grids.
 Cases 9 through 12 are net-zero for both electricity and heating.
 Case 5a is Case 5 but only for the NG heating home.
 Case 5b is Case 5 but only for the ASHP heated home.
 2050 electricity system demand and simulations include EV charging but the typical home monthly electricity bill and total bill do not so comparisons can be made with 2022 table values.

The impact on system capacity factor and electricity rates is shown in Table 3-3, below, for 5 simulation cases in each of 2022 and 2050.

The simulation shows the capacity factor in 2022 was 71% with no heating electrification and 32% to 39% if we had electrified all space heating with one of the four net-zero heating options (Case 9 to 12).

The 2050 year is particularly interesting because the additional loads from electrification of transportation help to improve the power system’s operating capacity factor (ie: the load profile is flatter) because electric vehicles (EVs) use electricity all year rather than just in the winter in the case of heating loads. The

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simulation shows the capacity factor in 2050 was 79% with no heating electrification of existing buildings (pre 2025 construction) and 40% to 46% if we had electrified space heating in all buildings with one of the four net-zero heating options (Case 9 to 12).

Table 3-3
Electrification Impact on Grid Capacity Factor and Electricity Rates

Simulation Case	System Cap'y Factor	Elect'y Rates ¢/kWh	Monthly Elect. Bill
2022 – Case 1, no electrification, \$0 CO ₂ Tax (*)	71%	14.9	\$112
2022 – Case 2, no electrification, \$65 CO ₂ Tax (*)	71%	15.3	\$114
2022 – Case 3, no electrification, \$170 CO ₂ Tax (*)	71%	15.9	\$119
2022 – Case 8, NZ Grid, ASHP+NG<4C, \$170 CO ₂ Tax	63%	18.6	\$153
2022 – Case 10, ASHP+ERH, \$170 CO ₂ Tax (†)	33%	43.4	\$690
2022 – Case 13, NZ Grid, NG Htg, \$170 CO ₂ Tax	71%	17.6	\$132
<hr/>			
2050 – Case 1, EVs & NG htg, \$0 CO ₂ Tax (*)	79%	14.4	\$108
2050 – Case 2, EVs & NG htg, \$65 CO ₂ Tax (*)	79%	16.0	\$120
2050 – Case 3, EVs & NG htg, \$170 CO ₂ Tax (*)	79%	18.7	\$140
2050 – Case 8, EVs, NZ Grid, ASHP+NG<4C, \$170 CO ₂ Tax	69%	24.3	\$201
2050 – Case 10, EVs, NZ, ASHP+ERH, \$170 CO ₂ Tax (†)	41%	39.7	\$632
2050 – Case 13, EV's, NZ Grid, NG Htg, \$170 CO ₂ Tax	79%	23.7	\$178

Notes: All dollars are in constant 2022\$.

Net-zero simulations use ASHPs with Supplementary ERH backup.

All cases in 2050 include electrific'n of all htg loads in new buildings (post 2024).

(*) these cases allow NG generation to be used in the electricity system.

(†) Case 10 is net-zero - no NG is used for electricity or heating.

The cost of electricity for EV charging is not included in the 2050 monthly bill.

A comparison of Case 3 with Case 10 in 2022 or in 2050 in Table 3-3 shows that there is a substantial cost to consumers in the widespread deployment of ASHPs for heating existing buildings (pre-2025 construction). The cost is driven by three major factors – the drop in capacity factor (poor utilization of fixed assets), the cost of decarbonizing the electricity grid and the cost of expanding the electricity system to enable it to displace NG heating using ASHPs. Comparing Case 8 with Case 10 in either 2022 or 2050 shows the cost of expanding the electrical grid to eliminate NG use for space heating in existing buildings represents the largest fraction of the monthly bill increase.

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Another important observation from Table 3-3 is that if we look at Case 13 in either 2022 or 2050, we see that the electricity grid has achieved net-zero at an affordable cost. However, we still need to displace NG from the heating loads of existing buildings. If a clean source of heat were available to displace natural gas for that purpose, a significant savings can be realized by not having to expand the electricity system to provide that heat.

The main purpose for the Two Pathways report being prepared by BI is to answer the question: “can a district heating system (TN with TES) economically provide building heating compared to electrification with ASHPs?”.

The MIDAC simulation studies show that the emissions from the electricity system and natural gas system drop as we transition to cleaner energy systems. However, what clean generation choices we make has a major impact on electricity rates. In the MIDAC simulations we chose to minimize the cost of operating the electricity system. Using RNG combustion turbines even with higher fuel cost proved cheaper than other generation choices or electrical storage. Unfortunately, RNG has limited availability. MIDAC and BI limited RNG use for making electricity in Ontario to 6 TWh annually for the simulations. The resulting emissions for 3 simulation cases in each of 2022 and 2050 is shown in Table 3-4 below. Comparing Case 3 and Case 6 in either 2022 or 2050 shows that installing ASHPs prior to conversion to a zero-emission electricity system reduces total emissions for space heating by less than 10%.

**Table 3-4
Electrification Impact on Carbon Dioxide Emissions**

Simulation Case	Elect Sys Emissions Mt/yr	Furnace Emissions Mt/yr	Total Emissions Mt/yr
2022 – Cases 1, 2 & 3, no electrification (*)	6.0	22.1	28.1
2022 – Case 6, ASHP+ERH (*)	25.9	0.0	25.9
2022 – Cases 9 to 12, heating electrif'n, (z)	0.0	0.0	0.0
2050 – Cases 1, 2 & 3, EVs & NG Htg (* †)	40.8	22.1	62.8
2050 – Case 6, EVs+ASHP+ERH (* †)	60.9	0.0	60.9
2050 – Cases 9 to 12, EVs + htg electrif'n (†z)	0.0	0.0	0.0

Notes: Net-zero simulations use ASHPs with Supplementary ERH backup.
 (*) these cases allow NG generation to be used in the electricity system.
 (†) these cases include electrif'n of all htg loads in new buildings (post 2024).
 (z) these cases are net-zero - no NG is used for electricity or heating.

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4. Surplus Clean Electricity & Discarded Thermal Energy

One of the more misunderstood characteristics of a zero-emission electricity system is that it can waste a lot of available clean energy production capability. The reason is that electricity demand varies significantly during a day, a week and across seasons. Ontario does not have sufficient low-cost electric storage capability so the excess production during low demand periods needs to be turned off or curtailed. The production capability is wasted unless we can find better uses for that surplus clean electricity.

One of the goals of the simulation is to forecast the amounts of surplus clean energy that is available and the associated effective capacity factor. The capacity factor is important because it will determine if the equipment needed to use the surplus energy can be economically installed. There are two types of clean energy that are available from electricity production. The one most obvious to people is the curtailed surplus electricity mentioned above. But some electricity generation technologies reject heat as part of the electricity making process. Power plants that use a thermodynamic process to make electricity also discharge a lot of lower temperature heat in their steam turbine cooling water. NG, RNG and nuclear plants are in that category. The rejected heat from NG plants has emissions associated with the fuel combustion but once the heat has been produced there is no point wasting it. Solar photovoltaic plants produce clean rejected heat from their panels. Table 4-1 below summarizes the amount of rejected heat from the production of electricity.

**Table 4-1
Rejected Heat from Electricity Production**

Generation Technology	Ratio of Thermal Energy Rejected to Electricity Produced
NG-CCGT plant (mixed fleet) (see note)	1.2
Nuclear plant (mixed fleet)	2.0
Solar Photovoltaic (mixed fleet)	4.0
Hydroelectric	0.0
Wind Turbine	0.0

Notes: NG-CCGT rejected heat has emissions associated with the fuel combustion.
RNG-CCGT rejected heat is not included above because the operating capacity factor of RNG plants is not high enough to economically recover the heat.

For the CCGT and nuclear thermodynamic cycles above, the rejected heat in the cooling water varies in temperature depending on the time of year and the type of cooling system used (i.e.: open lake cooling, closed atmospheric air cooling or

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open evaporative atmospheric air-cooling system). The rejected heat in the cooling water can be made more useful if some higher temperature steam extracted from the electricity production process is used to raise the cooling water temperature sufficiently for space and water heating.

The solar photovoltaic rejected heat is also weather dependent with higher temperatures in the summer and lower temperatures in the winter. The rejected heat from solar PV is calculated based on the uncurtailed capability not the actual electrical output. This is done because solar PV panels produce heat even when the actual electricity output is curtailed (reduced by the inverters).

Rejected heat can be made more useful with community thermal networks (TNs) and thermal energy storage (TES) facilities. If required, industrial sized heat pumps can also be used to boost the temperature of other community heat sources to a more useful value. TESs can store the rejected heat and discharge the heat later to a TN when heating demand is much higher on very cold days. Community TESs can be very large (up to 100 GWh each) and store heat across seasons. For example, rejected heat in the spring, summer and fall can be stored in the ground for use during the winter heating season. Seasonal community TES facilities are approximately 100 times cheaper per delivered energy unit than electrical battery storage facilities, based on some projects recently completed in Europe.

MIDAC's simulation forecasts the surplus clean electricity and surplus thermal energy that can be produced by the electricity system for the supply mix chosen by the simulation user to minimize emissions and electricity rates.

Table 4-2, below, summarizes the surplus energy quantities available from a net-zero electricity system. The table also shows the available operating capacity factor (CF) of that surplus electricity and thermal energy if we wanted to use the energy to reduce the amount of electrification we need to achieve our net-zero goals.

A closer look at Case 13 in both 2022 and 2050 in Table 4-2 shows that if we achieve net-zero on the electricity system there is more than sufficient surplus thermal energy (and also some surplus electrical energy) to heat existing buildings which have a space heating requirement of 104 TWh, provided there was a district heating system (TN with TES) in the community to supply that heat.

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**Table 4-2
Surplus Energy Available from Electricity Production**

Simulation Case	Surplus Electricity TWh / CF	Surplus Thermal Energy TWh / CF
2022 – Cases 1 to 3, no electrification (*)	1.3 / 3%	178.6 / 69%
2022 – Case 6, ASHP+ERH (*)	0.7 / 2%	238.1 / 31%
2022 – Case 10, ASHP+ERH (z)	158.4 / 51%	331.3 / 53%
2022 – Case 13, Net-zero Grid, NG Htg	9.3 / 14%	181.5 / 71%
2050 – Cases 1 to 3, EVs & NG htg (* †)	0.0 / 0%	282.5 / 72%
2050 – Case 6, EVs+ASHP+ERH (* †)	0.0 / 0%	342.6 / 39%
2050 – Case 10, EVs+ASHP+ERH (†z)	164.6 / 47%	508.4 / 60%
2050 – Case 13, Net-zero Grid, NG Htg	26.4 / 22%	369.7 / 74%

Notes: All net-zero simulations use ASHPs with Supplementary ERH backup.
 (*) these cases allow NG generation to be used in the electricity system.
 (†) these cases include electrif'n of all htg loads in new buildings (post 2024).
 (z) these cases are net-zero - no NG generation is used to make electricity.

The bar charts in Chart 4-1 and Chart 4-2, below, provide a more visual representation of the surplus amounts available in 2022 and 2050 when the electricity system emissions reach zero.

A vertical black bar is located at a value of 135 TWh that represents all the space heating energy required in a normal weather year for NG heated existing buildings, including approximately a 30% allowance for losses in a district heating and TES system if they were provided for consumers to use.

What is particularly important from the two charts is that a net-zero electricity system combined with a ban on the use of NG (Cases 9 to 12) will result in very large amounts of surplus clean electricity and surplus clean thermal energy being rejected. The surplus quantities are each larger than the useful electrical energy supplied for space heating of existing buildings.

Even Case 13, which has a net-zero electricity system before heating electrification of existing buildings, discards enough surplus thermal energy during electricity production to heat existing buildings that are currently heated with NG. Whereas in cases 9 to 12 there will be no TNs to make use of this

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clean surplus thermal energy because of electrification, in case 13 there could be.

Chart 4-1 Surplus Energy Available from Electricity Production in 2022 Simulations

Chart 4-2 Surplus Energy Available from Electricity Production in 2050 Simulations

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This suggests there may be a better balance between electrification using ASHPs and the provision of community district heating systems (TNs with TESs) as options to decarbonize our buildings' space heating needs. Since district heating systems are not economic in lower population density areas, we may choose to deploy different decarbonization strategies in low, moderate and high population density areas so that we minimize the waste of clean energy.

A more flexible decarbonization strategy should result in lower overall costs of decarbonization for the community. It will also lower the total amount of energy that needs to be produced from primary energy sources to supply our community energy needs.

The Boltzmann Institute is in the process of evaluating that strategy in their Two Pathways study for the federal government. This report is one component of the input data to that broader study.

5. The Case for Including Thermal Energy into Integrated Energy Plans

Generation technologies do not operate at full power constantly. Base-load plants have random outages, renewable systems are weather dependent on their output. When we set a zero-emission goal on the electricity system we are forced to fill in all production gaps using a zero emitting or carbon neutral technology. MIDAC attempted to fill in the production gaps using electrical storage. Unfortunately, the large difference between the higher winter peak and lower summer peak meant that storage facilities are underutilized. The low operating capacity factor caused the electricity rates to rise. Neither battery storage or pumped hydroelectric storage helped reduce electricity rates.

To minimize electricity rates MIDAC ran a series of simulations using combinations of additional zero emitting generation and additional RNG-CCGT generation. In all simulations, the use of RNG-CCGT generation resulted in the largest reduction in electricity rates. Even though RNG fuel is expensive the very low capital costs of RNG-CCGT plants compared to the higher costs of electricity storage resulted in lower electricity rates.

Unfortunately, RNG has limited availability. After a review of RNG availability, MIDAC and BI agreed to limit the use of RNG to at most 6 TWh of electricity production per year. This restriction was then used in the simulations to determine the new minimum electricity rates.

Table 5-1 below shows the capacities of each generation technology required to achieve the minimum electricity rates for the four net-zero cases (Cases 9 to 12)

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that were analyzed for space heating electrification of existing buildings in 2022 and 2050. Case 13 has been added to illustrate that the majority of electricity system expansion is for powering the ASHPs.

**Table 5-1
Capacity Requirements for Net-Zero Electrical Grid Using ASHPs**

2022 Grid (no EV electrification)	Hydro MW	Wind MW	Solar MW	Nuclear MW	RNG CCGT MW(*)	RNG SCGT MW(*)
Present 2022 Grid (*)	8,900	4,900	500	13,100	7,000	3,800
Case 9 – ERH	8,900	17,500	0	51,000	21,700	11,600
Case 10 - ASHP+ERH	8,900	17,000	0	35,400	31,100	10,800
Case 11 - ASHP+ERH<+4 C	8,900	18,500	0	50,700	21,900	11,600
Case 12 - ASHP+ERH < -8 C	8,900	25,500	0	42,800	28,500	11,600
Case 13 – NZ Grid, NG Htg (†)	8,900	7,500	2,000	11,600	6,100	3,700

2050 Grid (with EV electrification)	Hydro MW	Wind MW	Solar MW	Nuclear MW	RNG CCGT MW	RNG SCGT MW
Case 9 – ERH	8,900	19,500	0	63,200	24,400	13,100
Case 10 - ASHP+ERH Suppl	8,900	19,500	0	47,500	34,700	12,500
Case 11 - ASHP+ERH < +4 C	8,900	19,500	0	63,200	24,400	13,100
Case 12 - ASHP+ERH < -8 C	8,900	19,500	0	56,900	30,000	13,000
Case 13 – NZ Grid, NG Htg (†)	8,900	11,900	3,000	24,200	10,500	5,300

Notes: Capacities are rounded to the nearest 100 MW.
Storage did not reduce electricity rates when 6 TWh of RNG is available.
Because of the high winter peak demand, solar capacity increases electricity rates.
RNG capacity to serve load is CCGT, RNG reserve capacity is SCGT.
(†) Case 13 only has a net-zero electricity system, NG is used for heating.
(*) The 2022 grid uses NG fuel not RNG and most installed capacity is CCGT.

Table 5-2 below shows the total amount of new generation capacity that must be built in the next 25 years for each of the net-zero cases. If ASHPs are used exclusively for building heating, the required new generation capacity is well beyond Ontario’s best electricity grid construction experience in the 1965 to 1990 period.

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**Table 5-2
Total Capacity Requirements for Net-Zero Electrical Grid Using ASHPs**

2022 Grid (no EV electrification)	Total Generation Serving Load MW	Reserve Generation MW	Grand Total Generation MW
Present 2022 Grid (*)	34,400	3,800	38,200
Case 9 – ERH	99,000	11,600	110,600
Case 10 - ASHP+ERH	92,400	10,800	103,200
Case 11 - ASHP+ERH<+4 C	99,900	11,600	111,500
Case 12 - ASHP+ERH < -8 C	105,600	11,600	117,200
Case 13 – NZ Grid, NG Heating (†)	36,100	3,700	39,800

2050 Grid (with EV electrification)	Total Generation Serving Load MW	Reserve Generation MW	Grand Total Generation MW
Case 9 – ERH	116,100	13,100	129,200
Case 10 - ASHP+ERH Suppl	110,600	12,500	123,100
Case 11 - ASHP+ERH < +4 C	116,100	13,100	129,200
Case 12 - ASHP+ERH < -8 C	115,300	13,000	128,300
Case 13 – NZ Grid, NG Heating (†)	58,400	5,300	63,700

Notes: Capacities are rounded to the nearest 100 MW.
Reserve capacity is RNG-SCGT, Load serving RNG capacity is RNG-CCGT.
(†) Case 13 only has a net-zero electricity system, NG is used for heating.
(*) The 2022 grid uses NG fuel not RNG and most installed capacity is CCGT.

Case 13 shows that if heating for existing buildings could be provided by a district heating system in urban areas, the amount of new generation that needs to be constructed by 2050 is much more likely to be realizable.

To get a better appreciation of the magnitude of the peak winter demand and its impact on the installed generating capacity, MIDAC has prepared two peak demand charts for Ontario’s 2022 electricity system. The charts show the daily peak demand if we install ASHPs in all existing buildings currently heated by NG fuel.

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Chart 5-1
2022 Ontario Daily Peak Electricity Demand – NG Heating versus Hybrid ASHPs with NG Below +4 deg C Outdoor Temperature

Chart 5-1 above shows that the additional peak load is modest if we allow the use of NG for supplementary heat with the ASHPs. However, that option would not be net-zero.

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Chart 5-2
2022 Ontario Daily Peak Electricity Demand - NG Heating versus
ASHPs with Elect. Resist. Supplementary Heat

Chart 5-2 above shows that the additional peak load from the ASHPs approximately triples the peak demand. Unfortunately, that peak demand only occurs in the winter period. For the rest of the year that generating capacity is underutilized and must be paid for with higher electricity rates. Currently provincial energy policy would require all electricity system users to share the additional cost to operate the electricity system.

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MIDAC also prepared one peak demand chart Chart 5-3 for Ontario’s 2050 electricity system. The 2050 chart includes electrification of personal transportation (EVs), population growth, additional industrialization and electrification of all new (post 2024) building heat loads.

Chart 5-3
2050 Ontario Daily Peak Electricity Demand - NG Heating versus ASHPs with Elect. Resist. Supplementary Heat

The amount of new generation required to meet the very high winter peak demands shown in Chart 5-3 has never been built in Ontario in a 25-year period.

In 2022 the total generation required to reliably meet the peak load without electrification was 35,600 MW including reserve generation. The 2022 grid also included some plants that were being refurbished so the total installed generation was approximately 38,200 MW. By 2050 that total will need to be 123,100 to 129,200 MW including reserve generation, depending on which net-zero ASHP heating option is chosen by consumers.

MIDAC considers it impractical to more than triple the capacity of the existing electrical system in a 25-year period. Other options like TNs with TESs should be included in the energy planning process along with combinations of the available strategies.

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Recently the Ontario government and Ontario Energy Board (OEB) have proposed better integrated planning among the electricity sector, natural gas sector and other fuels sectors. This is certainly an important step in the right direction. However, MIDAC and BI believe the government should further expand the integrated planning to include thermal networks (TNs). TN's will help reduce the expansion of the electricity system to more realizable levels.

Consumers cannot independently develop TNs. TNs where they are economically practical must be provided as a service by either government or by private companies that are encouraged and regulated by government, just like sewers and water mains are a public service in non-rural areas.

This report highlights the significant amount of surplus energy (clean electricity and discarded thermal energy) that a future net-zero electricity system will create. TNs can use that surplus clean energy for space heating and water heating without creating environmental emissions. TNs are not new. In parts of the world where energy prices have been higher in the past, TNs have developed for economic reasons. Community TNs in higher density areas are popular in Europe and elsewhere. In fact, there are a few TNs in some of Canada's highest density communities like downtown Toronto and Markham's new city centre.

This report makes a case that government needs to get involved in evaluating where TNs are economically practical and then encourage their development through appropriate regulations or incentives. To ignore TNs will result in higher cost energy for consumers as we approach net-zero. Also, a significant amount of energy that is net-zero will be wasted if TNs are not available to non-rural consumers as an energy supply choice for their space heating and water heating.

This report does not study the requirements for high temperature TNs. However, with the development of Small Modular Reactors (SMRs) at Darlington, a study of the application of high temperature TNs should also be undertaken by the government. High temperature TNs can potentially achieve net-zero emissions in the industrial sector at lower costs because other options such as electric or net-zero fuels for high temperature heating are relatively expensive.

6. Conclusions and Recommendations

The analysis of various electrification options for building heating using the currently favoured approach by the federal government of using ASHPs with supplementary ERH shows that electrification on its own has the following problems:

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- Future monthly electricity bills for homes will increase nearly 6x with widespread deployment of ASHPs due to three cost factors:
 - The drop in the electricity grid capacity factor (winter peaking).
 - The rise in electricity consumption to power the ASHPs.
 - The higher cost of zero-emission generation compared to NG.
- Overall monthly energy bills for homes will more than triple. The 6x increase in electricity bills is offset by the elimination of NG bills in a net-zero future. However, the cost of writing off the NG stranded assets has not been included in this report.
- The electricity system capacity factor will drop approximately in half if we electrify space heating exclusively with ASHPs where natural gas is currently used. The winter peak is much higher than the summer peak. Generation capacity installed to meet the winter peak will be idle the rest of the year.
- The drop in electricity system capacity factor will cause electricity rates to approximately double not including general price inflation.
- The higher electricity rates combined with greater electricity use for ASHPs will result in a more than tripling of monthly total energy bills for consumers, not including general price inflation. Also, the higher capital cost of the ASHPs and the potential cost of upgrading the home's electrical distribution panel is an additional burden consumers will face that is not included in this report.
- In a net-zero electricity system the amount of surplus clean electricity and discarded thermal energy, which could be used for building heating, will each be larger than the electric energy supplied to consumers for their ASHPs.
- The amount of new zero-emissions dependable generating capacity required to achieve net-zero by 2050 is much larger than Ontario's historical ability to add new electrical capacity in that period. Adding the required transmission and distribution capacity may be challenging in some areas. Distribution, in particular, may require complete replacement of last mile infrastructure with at least triple the capacity when EV's are also considered; adding new equipment in parallel with existing transformers, wires, etc. may not be acceptable to consumers in many areas.
- Based on experience with heating buildings in cold climate countries in Europe and Asia it would be prudent to investigate alternatives to widespread ASHP electrification of building heating.

This report also recommends that community thermal networks be included in the integrated energy planning process in the province of Ontario along with the planning of the future supplies of electricity, natural gas and other fuels. TN's will help reduce the expansion of the electricity system to a more realizable level.

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However, to include community thermal networks into the planning process, communities will need to be funded to undertake building heating planning as part of the integrated energy planning process. European communities have engaged in heating planning and should be a useful source of information for Ontario communities.

7. References

- R1 OSPE Report, March 2016, “Ontario’s Energy Dilemma: Reducing Emissions at an Affordable Cost”. Available at: <https://ospe.on.ca/wp-content/uploads/2024/11/2016-ontario-energy-dilemma.pdf>
- R2 IESO Report, 2024 Ontario Planning Outlook. Available at: <https://www.ieso.ca/en/Sector-Participants/Planning-and-Forecasting/Annual-Planning-Outlook>
- R3 US generation costs are from NREL Annual Technology Baseline, 2024 V2. Available at: <https://atb.nrel.gov/electricity/2024/data>

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Appendix A - Modeling and Simulation Assumptions

MIDAC developed a simplified grid analysis model for OSPE to evaluate the impact of decarbonizing the power system. The model runs on an MS-Excel spreadsheet. The model was originally designed to evaluate:

- the amounts of installed capacity of various technologies needed to meet IESO future forecasted demand and NERC reliability requirements,
- the amounts of surplus (curtailed) clean electricity, in the absence of exports, as we decarbonize the power system,
- the amounts of carbon dioxide emissions from the electricity system if NG plants are permitted to be used as the backup/reserve resource, and,
- the cost of operating the electricity system and the resulting average retail rates for electricity in cents/kWh.

The MIDAC grid model is a modified version of a grid energy balance model developed by Dr. Gene Preston, in Texas. Dr. Preston's model was used to study the electrical grid impact from the URI winter storm in 2021 to help develop strategies to avoid similar power outages for future storm events.

The MIDAC grid model for Ontario required several changes to ensure it could properly forecast the more detailed information that MIDAC wanted to extract from the simulation. These changes included:

- A more detailed cost model that differentiated debt and equity, including a construction expenditure S-curve for each generation technology type to calculate capitalized interest charges from overnight capital costs.
- A simplified transmission, distribution and regulatory cost model based on a fixed ratio of those costs to generation costs based on IESO reported historical costs.
- A simplified generation dispatch algorithm to reflect how generation is dispatched in Ontario's hybrid energy market to calculate curtailed quantities of clean electricity and rejected thermal energy from electricity production.
- A mechanism for the grid simulation user to select RNG instead of NG generation to study the cost of driving emissions to net-zero. RNG is carbon neutral and can be used instead of alternative clean generation and storage.

The model uses a reference year for which historical data is available to calibrate the variability of clean generation in a typical year. Hydroelectric, wind, solar and nuclear production is normalized each hour in per unit values (0 to 1) relative to the installed nameplate capacity in the reference year. The per unit values for

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each technology is then used in the study year to forecast the hourly available capability of that technology from the proposed installed capacity in the study year. The use of this methodology is important because it captures real life variations in available production due to random plant outages and weather changes. The unavailable capacity may require backup generation or storage to meet the load demands in a particular hour. Meeting the firm load requirements every hour with less than a 10% failure rate for the whole year is a North American Electricity Reliability Corporation (NERC) reliability requirement for the high voltage power system. The NERC requirement is mandatory in Ontario and in other interconnected power systems in North America.

For practical purposes, the 10% failure rate per year is achieved in the MIDAC grid model by:

- using a reference year with normal weather to forecast the available capacity in the study year,
- meeting the firm load requirement every hour in the study year, and
- providing an additional amount of reserve capacity equal to 15% of the peak hourly demand for the study year using RNG-SCGT plants. The fixed cost of the reserve capacity is included in the cost of operating the electricity system. The RNG-SCGT plants do not have variable operating costs in the simulation because the reserve generation does not operate in a normal weather year.

No single year represents a perfect set of supply-demand data. Each year includes individual circumstances such as random outages that affect all generation differently every year. Also, weather changes affect both consumer load and generation output especially for hydroelectric, wind and solar plants. Averaging several years of data to create an “average year” would eliminate hourly variations in supply and demand that create both the surplus zero-emission energy and the backup generation requirements we are interested in quantifying. The quantity of those two will impact the cost of operating the power system. Therefore, the simulation must preserve the variability of generation plant production to provide realistic forecasts of future costs and electricity rates.

The MIDAC grid model uses hourly data from one reference year to forecast the variability of output from each generation technology. This approach will create realistic peaks and valleys in supply due to weather and random outages, but the variations will not necessarily align with real time conditions in future years. The reduced hourly fidelity in future years is considered acceptable because it is more important to capture the production variability that creates the additional costs to operate the electricity system.

To undertake an analysis of future years we need forecasts of consumer load, and to a lesser extent, import and export quantities. Fortunately, the IESO

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provides hourly load demand forecasts into the future for 25 years as part of their long-term planning process. The IESO does not currently provide hourly data for imports and exports for future years.

Surplus zero-emission electricity is an hourly phenomenon created by hourly clean generation output capability that exceeds hourly consumer demand. The model creates the hourly forecasted supply and demand data for future years as described below.

The model can be set up with input data to study either the high voltage (HV) bulk electricity system (BES) or the entire electricity system including the low voltage (LV) distribution system. However, the user needs to decide which analysis they want to perform and then make sure all input data aligns with that decision. The LV distribution system contains most of the solar generation, some wind generation and a small amount of hydroelectric and natural gas/bio-fuel generation. Any generation in the distribution system lowers the net demand that the HV system sees. The distribution embedded generation is very weather dependent and therefore creates more variability in the consumer net load demand that the HV system provides. The IESO hourly data which is publicly available applies to the HV electricity system. For that reason, MIDAC has performed the simulation analysis for this report for the HV electricity system.

The reference year hourly production data the IESO provides does not include any curtailed generation due to lack of demand. To properly model the available production capacity each hour the model needs to add back in the curtailed amounts. Fortunately, the IESO provides real time generation capability data for nuclear, wind and solar generation. But that data is not perfectly accurate because the wind and solar capability is produced by IESO weather models. MIDAC therefore had to adjust the hourly capability data to ensure it did not fall below the actual output data. MIDAC also had to do the same for nuclear capability because some hours showed nuclear capability lower than the actual output.

The hourly capability of hydroelectric generation is not reported by the IESO. Hydroelectric hourly curtailment is reported by Ontario Power Generation (OPG) to the Ontario Energy Board (OEB) annually since 2022. Prior to 2022 OPG only reported hydroelectric curtailment quarterly in their financial reports. MIDAC added the OPG hourly curtailment data for 2022 to the actual hydroelectric production to determine the hydroelectric capability.

There are some hydroelectric plants that are not operated by OPG. The total installed capacity of these other producers is minor compared to OPG. These other producers do not report hourly curtailment data. The large hydroelectric facilities that OPG owns perform most of the hydroelectric curtailment when there

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is too much clean generation relative to the load demand. MIDAC's simulation therefore ignores the curtailment from non-OPG hydroelectric plants.

MIDAC's simulation model does not determine the hourly capability of NG and RNG plants. Those plants provide the system reserve and therefore never operate near their total fleet installed capacity during a normal weather year. MIDAC assumes any demand for their output can always be served by those plants during any simulation hour. Normalization of the NG and RNG hourly capability in the reference year is therefore not required. NG and RNG installed nameplate capacity in the study year is always considered available for simulation purposes.

Once the curtailment adjustments are made for hydroelectric, nuclear, wind and solar generation in the reference year, the simulation model then uses the adjusted normalized values to predict available production capability for each hour of the study year based on the forecasted installed nameplate capacities of each of those generation technologies in the study year. The available production capabilities are then used to meet load demand forecasts for the study year for each simulation study case.

Any hourly production deficiencies are then made up from either electrical storage, RNG-CCGT or NG-CCGT plants, in that order, to satisfy the load demand every hour in the year. To achieve net-zero emissions, the simulation user needs to increase other generation or storage to drive the NG-CCGT use to zero.

To accommodate BI's request to study several heating options, MIDAC expanded the model to include several heating hourly data sets in addition to the IESO traditional electrical loads. All the load data sets are now contained in the "Study Year Hourly Load Inputs" sheet. The model does not currently switch automatically between the heating load data sets for each heating option simulation case. The linkage between the appropriate heating data set and the simulation algorithms must be made for each study case in the "Study Year Energy Calcs" sheet and the results saved for that heating option.

Electricity Demand Modeling

The IESO 2024 Annual Planning Outlook (APO) provides hourly demands as seen by the generators on the HV system from January 1, 2025 to December 31, 2050. Those hourly demands include any transmission and distribution line losses but do not include export sales. IESO does not currently plan system expansion based on export sales because Ontario does not currently export firm electricity under long term contracts. Ontario only exports electricity when excess production capability is available on an interruptible basis.

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However, for revenue recognition purposes, MIDAC prefers to include any net revenue from imports/exports. IESO is likely to continue to be a net exporter of electricity in the future as it has been for many years to date. Interruptible electricity is priced at the wholesale market clearing price (often referred to as the spot market price). Interruptible electricity has a much lower market value than firm electricity.

For the revenue estimate, MIDAC has assumed the import and export quantities in 2050 will be the same as in 2022. Also, the expected HOEP price is assumed to be the same hourly price as in 2022. On that basis the net revenue from imports and exports on the energy market was calculated to be \$308 million in 2050.

In 2050 the actual energy price will be different than 2022. The power system is expected to operate at zero emissions where the marginal cost of production will be set by low fuel cost sources in all cases except RNG. However, because RNG is about 5x more expensive than NG, when RNG is setting the energy price the HOEP will be 5x higher than when NG was used to meet the export load demand in 2022 (our reference year in this report).

MIDAC undertook a separate simulation to forecast the 2050 HOEP price. The simulation was based on the marginal cost of production of the last generation technology dispatched on to meet the prevailing load demand. The 2050 load demand and supply mix for Case 12, Hybrid ASHP with ERH below minus 8 C was used in the simulation. The simulated net revenue from the 2022 hourly import and export quantities based on the forecasted 2050 HOEP price was calculated to be \$240 million.

The \$68 million difference between \$308 million and \$240 million in a system with a total annual cost of \$86 billion dollars a year is not material. Even the full revenue amount of \$308 million is not very material. However, MIDAC has retained the import/export net revenue calculation using the 2022 imports, exports and HOEP price so that the net exported energy revenues which are likely to occur in the future are included in the net cost of operating the electricity system.

Generating Capacity Modeling

The MIDAC grid model includes imports as a resource. The IESO 2024 Annual Planning Outlook does not provide hourly import quantities. It does mention that it plans to continue with the Ontario-Quebec capacity sharing agreement at least for several years. Ontario typically imports and exports energy to its neighbouring power systems. To get a more representative cost of electricity

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MIDAC has included the 2022 hourly import quantities as a zero-emission resource for studies of both the 2022 and 2050 years.

The installed capacities of generation technologies are selected by the simulation user. However, existing/refurbished hydroelectric and existing/refurbished nuclear plants are much cheaper than new plants. Therefore, the IESO forecasted installed capacities of all existing hydroelectric and nuclear plants are retained in all simulation cases. New hydroelectric and new nuclear capacity is added by the simulation user.

For cost minimization studies, the user needs to manually step through the capacity of new plants for each generation technology one at a time to minimize total system costs. The resulting capacities after the cost minimization runs are complete represent the new supply mix for the simulation case.

The MIDAC simulation model uses the year end installed capacities of various technologies throughout the reference and study years. In real life, plants may be out of service for extended scheduled maintenance or refurbishment. Therefore, it is necessary to adjust the reference year installed capacities so the total annual production for the reference year for each technology is the same as that reported by the IESO.

Use of RNG Capacity in the Model

RNG fuel is about 5x more expensive than NG. Gas turbine plants are the lowest cost plant per installed kW.

RNG availability is also limited to about 5% of the volume of the NG distribution system. MIDAC and BI have estimated that a maximum amount of electricity that can be generated from RNG to serve Ontario load is 6 TWh.

RNG plants are divided into two types. RNG-SCGT (lower efficiency) plants and RNG-CCGT (higher efficiency) plants. RNG-SCGT plants are used for reserve generation because they are lower in capital cost and if they do not operate much the fuel costs have very little impact on system costs. Since the simulation only considers normal weather and does not consider unusual equipment outages, the reserve generation will never run in the simulation. Reserve generation is included in the simulation to meet the NERC reliability criteria and to account for the cost of that equipment in the total system operating costs for the year.

RNG-CCGT plants are more expensive than RNG-SCGT plants, but they operate more efficiently. More efficient plants are preferred when serving load because their higher efficiency will mitigate operating costs. Previous simulation studies

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have determined that some RNG generation capability can be much more cost effective than installing more non-combustion generation with storage, provided that the RNG-CCGT running time is not too great. The 6 TWh limit on electricity from RNG fuel use ensures the RNG-CCGT fleet running time is not too large.

Generating Plant Capital Cost Modeling

The capital value of existing/refurbished hydroelectric and existing/refurbished nuclear plants are estimated from OPG annual financial reports, not from the NREL data base of new power plant costs.

All other generation technology overnight capital costs are estimated using the 2022 NREL data base of new power plant costs and electrical storage costs.

Operating and maintenance costs can be fixed or variable. Fixed costs are those incurred regardless of the amount of energy produced. Variable costs are those incurred only when energy is being produced. An example of a fixed operating costs is the labour cost to operate the plant. An example of a variable operating cost is the fuel needed to make electricity. Both fixed costs and variable costs are modelled in the simulation.

The MIDAC simulation model uses an expenditure S-Curve over the typical project duration to estimate the additional capitalized cost created by the interest paid on debt during construction. The interest rate for debt and the ratio of equity to debt allowed by the energy regulator are user inputs to the simulation. The following project durations are used in the simulation to calculate the contribution to capitalized values from interest during construction:

Hydroelectric	10 yrs
Pumped Hydro Storage	10 yrs
Nuclear	8 yrs
CCGT/SCGT	4 yrs
Wind	3 yrs
Solar	2 yrs
Battery Storage	2 yrs

Average Retail Electricity Rate Modeling

Ontario retail electricity prices are established based on the consumption patterns of each of several consumer classes from Residential Class to Large Industrial Class. Also, each consumer class has different components and rates

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of charges for those components. Small consumers like residential and small commercial consumers pay a monthly fixed charge (mainly for distribution system costs) and a volumetric rate for the quantity of electricity they use in kWh. Larger consumers pay those 2 components plus a peak power (kW) demand charge if they use power during the day and a poor power factor charge if they have too much inductive or capacitive loads. The latter is used to pay for the higher power system losses incurred to serve that consumer which are not captured by the customer's electricity meter.

This report and the simulation model does not differentiate among the various consumer classes or billing components. The average electricity rate calculated in the MIDAC simulation is simply the total system cost divided by the total annual production. This simplification is considered acceptable when studying the cost of various generation options to meet future consumer demand.

Storage Operation Modeling

There are several ways to operate storage depending on whether the goal is to maximize revenue for the storage facility owner or to minimize the cost of electricity to the consumer. Currently there is not much storage on the Ontario power system. In total there is approximately 1,500 MW of effective nameplate rating of storage power capacity with less than about 15,000 MWh of energy storage capability among all the dams and pumped hydroelectric facilities. All the facilities are operated to maximize revenue for the storage facility owner.

The MIDAC simulation model is set up to use storage to minimize the cost of electricity to the consumer and to minimize overall power system emissions to the environment. That means the following strategies are incorporated into the storage calculation:

- Storage is not recharged with NG or RNG generation. It is only charged with low variable cost clean generation sources (hydroelectric, nuclear, wind and solar) and only when surplus capacity is available in each hour.
- Storage is only used to supply energy demand when low variable cost clean generation sources are insufficient to meet prevailing demand in that hour.
- When storage is full, surplus clean generation in that hour is curtailed (shut down).
- Curtailed values are summed to provide an indication of how much clean energy goes unused in the year by the supply mix chosen by the simulation user.

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Appendix B – Discussion of Simulation Uncertainties

Computer simulations of real systems require that we make some simplifying assumptions to keep the labour effort and cost of the simulation reasonable. The simplifications introduce uncertainties in the results that users of the simulation results should be aware of. This appendix discusses and estimates the magnitude of the more significant uncertainties.

Weather Uncertainties and Their Impact on Heating Loads

One of the most significant assumptions is choosing the normal weather year that is used to run the simulations. Weather impacts both traditional electrical loads and the new space heating electrification loads we are trying to analyse with the simulation model.

Traditional IESO electrical loads include electrical demand for lighting, appliances, fans, motors and electronic equipment. The traditional electrical load also includes some homes which have historically been heated by either resistance heaters or heat pumps of various vintages. In Ontario we have historical hourly demand data for traditional electrical loads. But that data is intimately associated with the specific weather in the years the data is collected.

Hourly historical natural gas (NG), propane and heating oil demand for buildings is not available in Ontario. We have natural gas monthly consumption data at a much higher aggregated level. That data needs to be combined with census data to estimate the heating demand. NG Heating demand for space heating can be modelled using heating degree hours. Other heating demand for cooking, water heating and clothes drying is less amenable to modelling because people's behaviour with respect to those other heating loads is less predictable than heating degree hours.

The MIDAC simulation uses space heating hourly demand for existing buildings based on an analysis done by BI staff of NG consumption and heating degree hours. The data is time shifted using a first order thermal lag due to building thermal mass. Hourly heating data was produced by BI for 6 years from 2018 to 2023. Bi has estimated that the annual total space heating demand uncertainty is + or – 10% and the uncertainty in the hourly variation is + or – 5 %.

Because weather affects both traditional electrical demand and new electrification loads, it is important to align the electrical demand year and the new electrification loads with that same year. This of course is possible with

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historical years like 2022 when we simulate what that year’s electrical load would have been if we had electrified space heating by various heating technologies.

Unfortunately, future years like 2050 pose a more difficult simulation problem. Both the traditional loads and the new electrification loads are all subject to speculation on what the actual weather will be in that future year and at a specific hour. MIDAC does not have a weather model that can produce reliable hourly data for both traditional electrical loads and new electrification heating loads.

For future years MIDAC has relied on the IESO 2024 Annual Planning Outlook for forecasts of future electricity demand from 2025 to 2050. That forecast includes electrification of all heating loads for new buildings constructed post-2024 but does not include any heating loads for existing buildings constructed pre-2025. The IESO uses an elaborate modelling approach where it moves the hourly demand data forward and back to arrive at a normal weather year hourly demand. The process is described in the IESO’s 2024 APO “Demand Forecast Methodology” report.. Unfortunately, IESO does not publish the hourly heating degrees for their “normal weather year”. Therefore, MIDAC cannot align its hourly heating loads for existing building with the IESO’s hourly heating loads for new buildings..

MIDAC chose a normal year from the hourly heating data available from BI for 2018 to 2023. MIDAC chose 2022 as the normal weather year from the following data:

Year	Annual Energy TWh(th)	Peak Demand GW(th)
2018	108.6	58.7
2019	110.7	56.6
2020	92.7	44.3
2021	91.0	44.7
2022	103.9	51.5
2023	86.3	53.4
6-yr average	98.9	51.5

2022 has a total space heating energy demand 5.1% higher than the 6-year average. But 2022 has a peak heating demand the same as the 6-year average. In a low emission power system like the Ontario power system, the total cost of operation is approximately 90% associated with the peak hourly demand and only 10% is associated with fuel cost. Therefore, it is more important to select a year that is closer to the average peak demand rather than the total energy

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demand. 2022 is therefore a more representative normal weather year. Even so the exact hour when the peak demand occurs in 2022 may not match the exact hour when the other forecasted electrical loads reach a peak. So, there is uncertainty that we have captured the correct total system peak demand of both the traditional electrical loads and new space heating loads.

Some comfort can be taken in that historically high system electricity loads in both winter and summer occur consistently with extreme temperature days. Therefore, ignoring this potential uncertainty is reasonable. Also, if a particularly extreme temperature day does occur, we have a 15% reserve capacity that we can call upon to serve the load for those few hours. Therefore, we do not need to build additional capacity for extreme temperature days. Also, the operating variable costs are only affected to a minor extent if the severe weather does not last for too long.

Consequently, the total installed capacity of the system only needs to reflect the normal weather year. BI has indicated their hourly heating demand uncertainty for their heating data is likely to be about plus or minus 5%. The 2050 heating load is 1.7x the IESO electrical load so the impact on the total installed peak electrical capacity requirement of 2.7x the IESO load will have an uncertainty of about $(1.7/2.7*5\%)$ which is approximately plus or minus 3%.

The total electricity system costs vary 90% with the installed peak load in a low emission power system so the overall system cost uncertainty is about plus or minus 3%.

Electricity rates vary directly with system costs and inversely with total energy consumption. If we assume there is no major increase in electricity consumed for the year because of a spike in demand caused by cold weather for only a few days, then the electricity rate uncertainty will also be plus or minus 3%.

Uncertainties in Modelling the Variability of Generation Capability

MIDAC modelled the generation capability using a reference year and the production variability of the generation in that same year. That production variability is affected both by weather for weather dependent generation and by random outages for all generation.

The simulation results show a capacity factor of about 83% for nuclear based on the reference year performance. However historically annual uncertainty of nuclear plant capability in Ontario can be expected to vary about plus or minus 5% due to differences in annual random outages.

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Nuclear capacity is the largest in our simulation and it also represents about 60% of the total system cost. Therefore, an uncertainty of 5% of nuclear capability will impact the required installed capacity and consequently the total system costs by about plus or minus 3%. Since consumer energy demand does not change with nuclear capability, the electricity rate will also have an uncertainty of plus or minus 5%.

Other Heating Loads that are Not Simulated

The MIDAC simulation does not include the 50% of other natural gas use, relative to space heating in existing buildings, that is currently used for non-space heating purposes (water heating, cooking, clothes drying, etc.). Those other heating loads are not all coincident with the peak space heating load. The peak space heating load for the normal weather year used in the simulation occurred in the middle of the night. If we assume that 1/3 of the other heating loads will appear coincident with the space heating load on a province-wide basis, we can expect an uncertainty in the peak total electrical load demand of about plus 10%. That uncertainty will impact the electricity system cost by an uncertainty of plus 9%.

The additional energy demand from the non-space heating load represents about 9% the total electrical load. Therefore, the increase in electricity rates due to system cost increases for more capacity will be offset by a reduction in rates due to an increase in energy use throughout the year. The uncertainty for ignoring non-space heating load will create no additional uncertainty for electricity rates. However, the increased consumption for the other heating loads, which is not part of this report, will of course increase the consumer's monthly bill. The increase in total energy demand and monthly cost is approximately 18% of the monthly cost identified in this report.

Minor Uncertainties and Total Uncertainty Estimate

The body of the report and Appendix A identified several minor uncertainties created by simplifications in modeling methods. However, in real physical systems independent overall uncertainties are typically determined using the square root of the sums of the squares of each uncertainty. The means total uncertainty, with contributing uncertainties of 3%, 3% and 9%, results in an overall peak demand uncertainty of 10% and a system cost uncertainty of 9% after scaling up to allow for electrification of non-space heating NG uses.

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Appendix C – Data Used in the Simulation

Most of the data described below and used in the simulation can be set by the simulation user.

The simulation uses the US National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) cost data sets except for existing/refurbished hydroelectric and nuclear plants. The existing/refurbished plant costs are obtained from OPG financial reports. The NREL data is based on US plant costs. The US\$ values are converted to CAN\$s by the exchange rate. The CAN\$/US\$ exchange rate can be set by the simulation user.

This report uses the US Energy Information Administration (EIA) data for the carbon content of natural gas (NG) fuel. Renewable Natural Gas (RNG) is considered carbon neutral in the simulation. However, due to limited availability of RNG in Canada, the amounts used in these case simulations is limited to 6 TWh per year for Ontario electricity production. RNG is used in these simulations to study net-zero supply mixes because even at 5x the cost of NG, RNG is more cost effective when operating at low capacity factors compared to other types of generation or storage technologies to provide the required backup service to other generation sources.

It is not practical to supply RNG directly to a power plant when NG is used extensively by consumers. The RNG is assumed to be supplied using contractual offset contracts. Essentially, whenever an RNG plant operates it contractually requires an RNG supplier to inject the same amount of RNG into the NG system. What that means is that the RNG power plant is forcing other users of NG to burn RNG equal to the NG the power plant is using in real time. The RNG power plant pays for the additional cost of RNG to the RNG supplier. As the amount of NG decreases and RNG increases, some RNG will be delivered directly to the RNG power plant in the NG supply. The simulation model does not adjust the carbon content of the NG/RNG mix.

The MIDAC simulation does not take into account changes in the price of natural gas due to supply-demand imbalances or from any future reduced volume of NG and associated changes to the regulated price of NG.

The following data is used in the simulation analysis for this report.

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Financial Input Data:

1.35	USD to CAD conversion rate
5.0 %	Allowed Annual Interest Cost on Debt
60 %	Percentage of Capitalized Cost Financed by Debt
9.0 %	Allowed Utility Rate of Return on Invested Equity
15 %	Dependable Reserve to Meet NERC Reliability Criteria
14.4 \$/MWh	Market Price Below Which Hydroelectric Plants Curtail
6.7 %	Combined Trans & Dist'n Losses for New Electrical Loads

Installed Capacity of Legacy Generation

8,900 MW Existing/refurbished Hydroelectric Plants (lower cost than new)
10,775 MW Existing/refurbished Nuclear Plants (lower cost than new)

All other installed nameplate capacities are specified by the simulation user except NG generation. The simulation calculates the required NG production to fill any gaps in supply and demand. The user needs to provide enough clean generation capacity to drive the NG energy to zero in the simulation results for all net-zero supply mix studies.

Hydroelectric Plant Cost Data

1,673	\$/kW	Existing Hydroelectric Capital Cost
7,922	\$/kW	New Hydroelectric Overnight Capital Cost
125,550	\$/MW-Yr	Hydroelectric Operating and Maintenance Fixed Cost
11.45	\$/MWh	Hydroelectric Average Variable O&M Cost
100	years	Depreciation Period (straight line assumed)

Nuclear Plant Cost Data

3,657	\$/kW	Existing Nuclear Capital Cost
7,763	\$/kW	New Nuclear Overnight Capital Cost
236,250	\$/MW-Yr	Nuclear O&M Fixed Cost
17.28	\$/MWh	Nuclear Fuel, Rad Waste Cost and Variable O&M Cost
84.0	%	Nuclear Availability Factor
30	years	Depreciation Period (straight line assumed)

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Wind Turbine Cost Data

2,248	\$/kW	Onshore Wind Overnight Capital Cost
55,114	\$/MW-Yr	Wind O&M Fixed Cost
2.50	\$/MWh	Wind Energy Royalty Fee/Variable O&M Cost
30	years	Depreciation Period (straight line assumed)

Solar Photovoltaic Cost Data

1,937	\$/kW	Fixed Mount Utility Solar PV Overnight Capital Cost
29,994	\$/MW-Yr	Solar PV O&M Fixed Cost
2.50	\$/MWh	Solar Energy Royalty Fee/Variable O&M Cost
30	years	Depreciation period (straight line assumed)

Natural Gas CCGT Plant Cost Data

1,667	\$/kW	Natural Gas CCGT Overnight Capital Cost
46,035	\$/MW-Yr	NG-CCGT/RNG-SCGT O&M Fixed Cost
7,425	BTU/kWh	NG-CCGT Thermal to Electricity Conversion Factor
6.50	CAN\$/M.BTU	Industrial NG Fuel Cost per Million BTUs
2.90	\$/MWh	NG-CCGT Variable O&M Cost
51.17	\$/MWh	NG-CCGT Combined Fuel + Variable O&M cost
30	years	Depreciation period (straight line assumed)

Renewable Natural Gas CCGT Plant Cost Data

1,667	\$/kW	RNG-CCGT Overnight Capital Cost
46,035	\$/MW-Yr	RNG-CCGT/RNG-SCGT O&M Fixed Cost
7,425	BTU/kWh	RNG-CCGT Thermal to Electricity Conversion Factor
32.50	CAN\$/M.BTU	Industrial RNG Fuel Cost per Million BTU
2.90	\$/MWh	RNG-CCGT Variable O&M Cost
244.22	\$/MWh	RNG-CCGT Combined Fuel + Variable O&M cost
30	years	Depreciation period (straight line assumed)

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Renewable Natural Gas SCGT Plant Cost Data. (for reserve generation)

1,487	\$/kW	RNG-SCGT Overnight Capital Cost
35,100	\$/MW-Yr	RNG-SCGT O&M Fixed Cost
30	years	Depreciation period (straight line assumed)

Pumped Hydro Storage Cost Data

5,416	\$/kW	Pumped Hydro Storage Overnight Capital Cost
0	\$/kWh	10-hour Storage Included in Capital Cost
27,203	\$/MW-Yr	Pumped Hydro Storage O&M Fixed Cost
85.0	%	Hydro Storage Charging Energy Efficiency
85.0	%	Hydro Storage Discharging Energy Efficiency
1.0	%/month	Hydro Storage leakage
0.78	\$/MWh	Variable O&M Cost (fuel included in other gen'n costs)
100	years	Depreciation Period (straight line assumed)

Battery Storage Cost Data

336	\$/kW	Battery Storage Overnight Capital Cost for Power Rating
498	\$/kWh	Battery Storage Overnight Capital Cost for Energy Rating
83,700	\$/MW-Yr	Battery Storage O&M Fixed Cost
92.5	%	Battery Storage Charging Energy Efficiency
92.5	%	Battery Storage Discharging Energy Efficiency
5.0	%/month	Battery Storage leakage
0.00	\$/MWh	Variable O&M Cost (fuel included in other gen'n costs)
20	years	Depreciation Period (straight line is assumed)

NG Heating Furnace Cost Data

37.23	CAN\$/MWh(th)	Residential NG Cost (includes fixed mon. charge)
85.0%	%	Lifetime Furnace Efficiency

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Carbon Emission Related Data

0, 65, 170	CAN\$/t CO ₂	Canadian Carbon Price (Tax) – depends on case
0.0%	%	CH4 Leakage Rate Wellhead to Burner Face
85.0%	%	Lifetime Furnace Efficiency
180.6	kg CO ₂ /MWh	Average CO ₂ Emissions from Furnace Combustion
392.9	kg CO ₂ /MWh	Average CO ₂ Emissions from NG Generation

Thermal Energy Discharged During Electricity Production

Nuclear	2.0	MW(th) per MW(e)
NG & RNG CCGT	1.2	MW(th) per MW(e)
Solar PV	4.0	MW(th) per MW(e)
Hydroelectric	0.0	MW(th) per MW(e)
Wind	0.0	MW(th) per MW(e)

Typical Home Energy Usage Data

Traditional Electricity Usage (see note 1): 750 kWh/month or 9 MWh/year
NG for space heating: 13.0 MWh/year (useful heat, normal year)
NG for other heating: 6.5 MWh/year (useful heat, normal year)

Note 1: Traditional electricity usage prior to electrification does not include vehicle or heating electrification.

Transmission, Distribution and Regulatory Costs

Transmission and Distribution costs fixed at 45% of Generation costs
Regulatory costs fixed at 7% of Generation costs

